

The Elliott's Wave Theory: Is It True during the Financial Crisis?

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Abstract

In this study we apply the Elliott's Wave theory to the index S&P 500 for a period of three years, starting from the October 2008 and until December 31, 2011. An analytical forecast for the first half of 2012 has been carried out. Our principle empirical findings underline that the evolution of the first five months of 2012 will be even more turbulent, even if with a slightly bullish phase until May; then we will see a collapse of the financial markets (also in the light of the probable Greek bankruptcy), with a more pronounced Bear Market. If our estimates of the downturn of the financial markets were to prove correct, the immediate implications of this analysis would lead to an accommodating monetary policy, made up of further cuts to the official interest rate.

Keywords: Elliott's theory; Fibonacci's sequence; technical analysis; stock market; S&P 500 index

JEL Classification: G12, G17

1. Introduction

The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) is based on the principle that the current price of an asset fully reflects all available information relevant to it and that new information is immediately incorporated into the price. It assumes that there is a rational and unique way to use the available information and that all agents possess this knowledge.

Technical analysis is a method of evaluating securities by analyzing the statistics generated by market activity, such as past prices and volume. Ralph Nelson Elliott developed the Elliott's Wave theory in 1920, when trading decisions in stock markets were based on herd psychology and not on any technical analysis. During that period, stock prices moved in a chaotic manner, and when those prices compounded onto a chart, the resultant curves offered no clues as pertaining to price trends. In this confusing scenario, Elliott saw a method in the madness – he discovered that, despite the herd mentality and the resultant chaos, stock prices were indeed following a definite pattern.

In this research, we show a forecast of the S&P 500 index, until May 2012, using weekly data.

2. Theoretical Background

Elliott postulated that the prices of stocks, though influenced by investor psychology, traded in repetitive cycles. His assumption was based on one of the fundamental rules of physics – that every action is followed by a reaction. It is surprising to think that almost every technical indicator used today is inadvertently based on this principle. Thus, in many ways, Elliott was ahead of his times. For instance, when there is euphoria in the market and people buy, this results in an increased demand, the stock prices climb and subsequently the supply drops – this comprises the action. Now, while stock prices are fluctuating, some investors make transactions in anticipation of any rise and fall in prices for whatever reason, so that supply increases and demand drops along with the stock prices – this is the reaction. If combined, the action and reaction form a wave-like pattern, which, if interpreted correctly, can predict a stock's future price.

According to Elliott, herd mentality in general follows cycles of optimism followed by cycles of pessimism, and the same holds for the minds of the investors/traders. These are reflected as a sequence of predictable ups and downs in the stock market. The ups representing the dominant trend and the downs the corrective phase in a bullish market – and vice versa in a bearish market. Elliott discovered that the wave patterns made on the charts had the unique mathematical characteristics of what came to be known later as fractals – mathematical geometric structures that re-peat themselves infinitely on an ever-diminishing scale. By applying fractal mathematics to price movements in the market, Elliott developed his wave theory, so as to make market predictions based on collective crowd behaviour.

The main points of the Elliott's Wave theory can be summarized as follows. A stock's price chart makes a sequence of waves representing the dominant (or main) trend followed by a corrective phase, where the overall price movement is against the trend. The dominant trend, which can be upward or downward, depending upon the mood of the market, is always comprised of 5 waves while the corrective phase is always comprised of 3 waves, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Market trend in Elliott's view

Source: our elaborations.

Elliott also showed that the sum of the waves is a complete cycle of incrementing stimulus impulses – the correction is exactly equal to the sum of downward waves: the wave 1, 3, 5, b and the wave upward 2, 4, a, c downward. The difference between a bullish and a bearish wave is given by the greater extension of the pulse wave in one direction or another. However, the cyclic order that governs the movement of prices is expressed, in his opinion, with fluctuations of varying complexity and of scales of time. For this reason we can identify eight major waves (first degree), each of which is composed of eight intermediate waves (second degree, Figure 2).

Figure 2: Factorization of the Elliott's wave

Source: www.traderlab.com.

Finally, each intermediate wave may be subdivided into eight minor waves (third degree), the total of which completes the Elliott's construction.

In 1887 Charles Henry Dow wrote a series of articles noting that the direction of prices in each average appeared to be based on a set of rules, i.e. a share price reflects everything that is known about a stock; at any given time, there are 3 trends unfolding in the stock market; primary trends have 3 phases; volumes confirm the trend; a trend continues until a reversal signal.

Markowitz (1952) and Tobin (1958) showed that it was possible to identify the composition of an optimal portfolio of risky securities, given forecasts of future returns and an appropriate covariance matrix of share returns. The results of the four different portfolio constructions in du Plessis and Ward (2009) show that even under the constrained conditions of no short-selling and/or no more than 10% in any single security, the strategy works.

Chatterjee et al. (2002) provided a survey of findings describing the use of Fibonacci series and its underlying principles to predict future security price movements. Using Elliott's waves as a tool to predict securities price movements, they indicated how a carefully constructed system can generate profits, even under quite volatile conditions. In fact, most of the losses are generated during the contraction-trend movements, but are kept quite low. The profits generated during the trend are themselves quite large, and more offsetting than any losses.

Empirical results obtained by Bhattacharya and Kumar (2006) appear to corroborate the claim of technical analysts that there is some predictive utility associated with Fibonacci sequences used as filters in automated trading systems.

3. Main Characteristics of Different Waves

The main feature of the theory is the ability to predict. In fact, the mere knowledge of the five waves series makes it possible to identify the likely future development of a market. The starting point to begin an analysis may be the easy identification of the beginning of a cycle, whether bullish or bearish. However, the difficulties increase when trying to pinpoint the start of the so-called "counting waves", so as to give sufficient predictive value for investment decisions. The presence of many deviations, if compared to standard waves, requires considerably greater experience and skills for their identification, but the main elements of the theory alone are sufficient to dramatically increase the effectiveness, as opposed to normal technical analysis.

In order to correctly identify Elliott's waves, we present some observations regarding the

typical characteristics of these waves (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Our financial analysis on FTSE MIB (December 2009 – January 2012)

Source: our elaborations on Powerdesk Fineco data.

Wave “1” is the least significant, because it can identify a pattern of accumulation with constant volumes. It is generally confused with a strong rebound of the previous bear market and therefore many operators take advantage of this opportunity to open short-term positions. This is the reason for the heavy retraction that characterizes wave “2” (at least 66%), which then frequently forms the configuration of a double bottom. Wave “3” is statistically the strongest, both in terms of duration of time and of percentage of income, and for this reason five smaller-sized waves are usually defined. The reason for this phenomenon lies in the breaking of the maximum generated from the wave “1”, capable of generating buying signals affected by resistance phenomenon.

The corrective wave “4” is usually a complex and long-lasting correction, which frequently causes false technical signals. The reason of this important correction lies in excess bullish of wave “3”. Wave “5” can be considered the strongest impulse of movement, when we are in the presence of the end of a cycle of important dimensions, which sees bullish euphoria typical of the speculative phase of Dow (1887). On the contrary, wave “5” indicates the strongest impulse movement, and the previously described situation occurs when there is a big temporal cycle, typical of a bullish euphoria period.

As for wave “A”, it is very short-lived and is usually interpreted as a correction in a strong bull market. Numerous purchases ensure that the wave “B” redesigns a large part of the descent of the wave A, generating false technical signals (bull traps). It should be noted that wave “B” is composed of three waves, since it is a correction wave.

Finally we describe wave “C”, which is often more complex to compile, and can in fact manifest itself as a normal correction or as Flat Running Correction.

The wave counts of the impulsive and corrective patterns are Fibonacci numbers. Breaking down wave patterns into their respective sub-waves produces Fibonacci numbers indefinitely¹.

¹ In the Fibonacci sequence of numbers, each number is the sum of the previous two numbers, starting with 0 and 1. Thus the sequence begins: 0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, 55, 89, 144, 233, 377, 610,... By dividing one number in the sequence by the next, the resultant ratio begins with common fractions: 1, 1/2, 2/3, 3/5,... but after a while the result remains at

The sequence and the ratio are also being used to predict the stock market swings or oscillations and price targets. Eng (1997) and Plummer (1989, 1997) provided the outline for successfully using of the sequence. Fischer (1993), Hartle (1997), and Krausz (1998), however, concluded against the stand alone use of the sequence. They observed that although the Fibonacci sequence is used as a technical indicator, it is best used as a tool to supplement other technical analysis methodologies rather than a stand-alone technique.

4. The Elliott's Wave theory on Standard&Poor's 500

Now we would apply the Elliott's Wave theory to S&P 500, considering it as the most significant indicator of the world financial system.

The Figure 4 below shows the performance of S&P 500 in the financial time series 2009-2011, where the application of the Elliott's Wave theory seems to be very appropriate.

Figure 4: Elliott's wave on S&P 500 (August 2009 – June 2011)

Source: our elaborations on ProRealTime data.

Although we are in the presence of a Bear Market Rally, we prefer to call it a cyclical Bull Market, by virtue of the duration and extent of the movement.

With regard to the count of the waves, we must consider that:

- The maximum of the April 26th 2010 (1219 points) must be seen as the *Top of the Wave [A], Primary of "Bear Market Rally"*.
- The minimum of July 1st 2010 (1010 points) is considered as a wave [B] Primary (divided into three sub-waves as per protocol).
- The maximum of May 2011 (1371 points) is seen as wave [C] Primary (divided into five sub-waves). On this date we can also consider the Bull Market Cycle concluded (2009-2011).

At the time of writing we are probably in the midst of a baby Bear Market (coinciding with the predictions of a recession for 2012). The extent and strength of this "bear market" will be determined in the coming months.

Let us now analyze the most significant waves after May 2011:

- Wave I intermediate (stimulus) completed with a minimum on June 16th 2011 (1258 points).
- Wave II intermediate (correctional countertrend) ended up with the July 7th 2011 (1356 points).

- Wave III intermediate (stimulus) completed with a minimum on August 9th 2011 (1102 points). This should also have been the strongest of the 3 downward impulses.
- Wave IV intermediate (correctional countertrend) ended with the maximum on August 31st 2011 (1230 points).
- Wave V intermediate stimulus ended with the least to 1075 points.

Now we are in full-wave II Primary and as expected it is proving very generous. Wave 2 is being developed in accordance with (ABC) intermediate grade.

The graph forecast below gives us more information:

Figure 5: Elliott's wave on S& P500 (April – December 2011)

Source: our elaborations on ProRealTime data.

- Wave A intermediate has already ended in 1293 with maximum points. The maximum of 1293 points could also have been the maximum wave II Primary, but the movement in the area of points 124 on December 5th 2011 has permanently deleted this possibility.
- Wave B intermediate has already been completed with the minimum area of 1157 points. As mentioned before, this wave was “deeper” than expected.
- Wave C intermediate is still in place. The target box for this wave is visible in the figure (1315-1320/1330 in the spike).

If our calculations are correct, after the peak of a wave II Primary there will be no room for long-term positions. Everything that ensues will be traumatic for the financial market.

5. Forecast Analysis for 2012

The last seventy-five years have been marked by epochal changes that have brought the world to a kind of “overload” much greater than achieved in the previous 200 years. No coincidence that the real economy and the financial economy have reached unimaginable levels. The technological development of the last 70-80 years has been as rapid as to leaves one astounded. But recently we have begun to “invent” increasingly diverse tools in order to push growth. The creation of speculative bubbles has in fact led the world into a state of “Deadlock”. The economy is no longer strong enough to be able to grow at the same rate as before. Whilst emerging countries like China, India, and Brazil push, the development of Europe and the USA seems to have reached an asymptote. There is no impetus for further growth.

For some time now the de-leveraging phenomenon has started, and it will continue for many years, perhaps irreversibly. Moreover, in order to bounce back from disproportionate debt it will take more than a matter of a few months. In the context of a crisis and of uncertainty, those who are most exposed (in absolute terms) prefer to reduce their risks. To do this loans are reduced by decreasing the liquidity supply. Faced with rising credit costs, economic actors can no longer think to take out new debt to finance previous ones. They are, therefore, forced to liquidate assets so as to raise the necessary funds and prevent default.

In this context of crisis, lenders become increasingly wary, thus reducing credit allowances, requiring debtors to increase margin requirements to fund their positions or to reduce their debt exposure.

Thus, commences the process called the “financial accelerator”: debtors sell their assets, whilst creditors fear that the debtors are not being honest about their true financial health, thus further increasing their margins to warrant themselves from risk.

The banks stop loaning capital or start increasing their rates, in order to defend themselves from the risk of sudden insolvencies. This is a phenomenon that has already begun and that can be defined as self-fulfilling.

The weekly data, obtained from Powerdesk Fineco database, covering a three year period, commencing on October 2008 and ending on December 31st 2011.

Figure 6 below illustrates an analytical forecast of the Primary and Intermediate Waves for early 2012.

Figure 6: Elliott’s wave on S&P 500 (until May 2012)

Source: our elaborations on ProrealTime data.

In A-Wave V-Primary, which corresponds to the prospected date of February 2012, we shall have, most likely, the top of the wave cycle and the maximum point of the Bull Market.

The graph shows a hiccup of the index until May 2012. Let us look at some months which are characteristic of the stock market performance as January (when falls on the so-called “January effect”), i.e. a bullish movement that occurs regularly in January in equity markets, and the “Sell in May and go away, till St. Ledger’s day”, which falls in mid-September, coinciding with the event horse of St. Ledger Stakes. This is in consideration for the detachment of dividends for listed companies that takes place in the month of May. Between January and May is to create a channel bullish that, albeit with a tips, concludes his cycle in the fifth month of the year. The application of the Elliott’s theory confirms these trends since the primary A-B in the month of January 2012.

If the Elliot Wave Theory has correctly interpreted the market thus far, considering the macro data that is daily obtained (GDP growth, unemployment, housing market, soaring public debt) and the analysis of many leading indicators (Weekly Leading Index and Metric Grow Index), it is possible to foresee the approach a new period of economic contraction starting in the second quarter of 2012, which would encourage the start of a Bear market for numerous years.

6. Summary and Concluding Remarks

The analysis carried out in this paper has been conducted by following carefully the dynamics of the index S&P 500, from 2008 to 2011, applying the Elliott's Wave theory. The choice of this index is due to the fact that it represents a very relevant indicator of the health of US stocks and it reflects, essentially, the dynamic of world market. This because the index includes 500 titles (with a market capitalization of \$10 trillion) chosen primarily for their market size, liquidity and industrial grouping.

The selected data cover a period of three years, starting from the October 2008 and until December 31, 2011. An analytical forecast for the first half of 2012 was then carried out by applying the Elliott's Wave theory.

The major findings of our analysis show that, in the case of turbulent financial markets (such as those that we are experiencing) technical analysis and the Elliott's theory adequately reflect the realities of the financial markets.

If one explores the portfolios constructed by mean-variance Markowitz's (1952) model in the stages of turbulent market, compared with strategies pursued with technical analysis, we may notice that a portfolio constructed on the basis of the first model would have been highly at a loss compared to a different portfolio built with technical analysis. The reason of this lies on the fact that with the second model it would be easier to draw up strategies in the short term, liquidating positions, instead the complexity found in the alternative Markowitzian portfolio.

Therefore, the Elliott's Wave theory, as all the instruments of technical analysis, is proposed as a tool for analysis, able to seize opportunities for profit even in turmoil phases.

In a period of financial crisis started in October 2008 after the collapse of Lehman Brothers, all major Blue Chips in principal financial markets have suffered large losses during the same year: an event that could be predicted but hardly managed with traditional methods. The most diversified portfolios, in our sample period, depreciated by the same percentage of the index S&P 500, except corrections less wide of some defensive bonds and in certain market sectors, which have shown a different elasticity.

On the basis of our analysis, the evolution of the first five months of 2012 will be even more turbulent, even if with a slightly bullish phase until May; then we will see a collapse of the financial markets (also in the light of the probable Greek bankruptcy), with a more pronounced Bear Market.

If our estimates of the collapse of the financial markets were to prove correct, the immediate implications of this analysis would lead to an accommodating monetary policy, made up of further cuts to the official interest rate.

From an Italian perspective, however, structural reforms, postponed for a too long time but today in discussion, could strengthen credibility and reputation of the national institutions, with positive effects on financial markets.

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